

Leaf epidermal characteristics of melons in the family Cucurbitaceae Juss. in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, there has been a lot of adulteration, substitution of a certain plant parts for another among the melon species in the Cucurbitaceae family as a result of similarities of plant parts, due to the fact that these species are highly nutritious and medicinal and therefore well sought after by medical practitioners and students. Hence, study on the epidermal features of these plants was undertaken for easy identification. Five species of Cucurbitaceae, commonly called melons: *Citrullus lanatus* Thunb. Matsum and Nakai (watermelon – three varieties based on the skin colour viz. light green (A), deep green (B) and striped green (C)), *Citrullus Colocynthis* (L.) Schrad. (Egusi melon), *Cucumis melo* L. (sweet melon), *Cucumis sativus* L. (Cucumber), *Cucumeropsis mannii* Naud. (Syn. *C. edulis* (Hooker f.) cogn; (White-seeded melon), and *Cucurbita moschata* (Duch. Ex Lam.) Duch. Ex Poiret) (Musk melon), found in Nigeria were studied. Epidermal features in the species included anomocytic and anisocytic stomata, glandular multicellular, and peltate trichomes and other epidermal features. The epidermal cell shape is irregular with sinuous anticlinal walls in *C. colocynthis*, trapezoid with straight anticlinal walls in two varieties of *C. lanatus*, *C. sativus* and *C. mannii*, and irregular with straight anticlinal walls in *C. melo*, *C. moschata*, and a variety of *C. lanatus*. Stomatal index (SI) value are distinct for each species (9.01 in egusi melon and 5.30 in a variety of watermelon), being the highest and lowest in the Cucurbits studied. The study aims at improving taxonomic information on and the classification of these species. This study has successfully provided additional taxonomic characters in lieu of leaf epidermal features for the purpose of checking adulteration, substitution, and fraud carried out on these species.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The family Cucurbitaceae is a widespread family consisting of 118-122 genera and 900 species of monoecious or dioecious herbs and erect shrubs [1]. The family is mainly distributed in tropical and subtropical regions with relatively few species growing in the temperate regions of the world. Cucurbitaceae family is among the economically most important plant families [2-7]. The family includes economically important food crops such as *Citrullus lanatus* (watermelon), *Cucumis melo* (sweet melon), *Cucumis sativus* (cucumber), *Cucurbita pepo*, *Cucurbita moschata* (musk melon) [8], and *Lagenaria siceraria*, bottle gourd, are used as vessels in African and Asian cultures [9-11].

The cucurbit does not have any close relatives.

All the species that are cultivated belongs to the sub-family Cucurbitoideae. The fruit of *Cucurbita maxima* Duch. ex Lam is the largest known fruit of all flowering plants. Most of the Nigerian cucurbits are indigenous, cultivated at subsistence level by farmers, but some are exotic and sold very expensive in the market. Cultivation of a typical species of cucurbit is familiar to most people. The plant grows vigorously in warm and hot weather with lots of water [12].

About three genera of Cucurbitaceae bear the common name, melons. They are *Cucumis*, *Citrullus* and *Cucumeropsis*. The genus *Cucumis* includes *C. melo* (sweet melon), *Citrullus* includes *C. lanatus* (Watermelon) and

C. colocynthis (Egusi melon or brown seeded melon) and *Cucumeropsis* is represented by one species in Nigeria, *C. mannii* (White-seeded melon or Mann's Cucumeropsis). *Cucurbita moschata* (Squash melon or Pumpkin) has non-edible seeds, which are usually mixed with the edible brown-seeded melon, and sold in the market as just brown-seeded melon to misguide buyers [13].

Citrullus colocynthis is native to tropical Africa and highly drought tolerant. A relative of watermelon, productivity is enhanced during dry, sunny periods and reduced during periods of excessive rainfall and high humidity. They can contribute substantially towards obtaining a balanced diet [14].

The watermelon, *Citrullus lanatus* like other Cucurbits, is warm-season annuals having long, prostrate vine growth; the vines readily attain lengths of more than 6 meters (20ft). Seeds are roasted and ground into tamma meal, a nutritious food with a pleasant nutty taste. Leaves and young fruits are utilized as green vegetables [15].

Cucumis sativus are 96 percent water, with a little fiber and only a few calories. In addition, it provides a good source of vitamins A, K, and C, as well as a large amount of potassium.

Cucumis melo cantaloupe, honey dew, sweet melon or muskmelon is a 'fruit' rather than a vegetable; the sweet, delicately flavored, juicy flesh of the pepo is eaten raw, often as a dessert. The species is variable with a considerable range of fruit types, many of them highly esteemed for their delicious flavor.

The white-seeded melon, *Cucumeropsis mannii* is a species of melon which is native to tropical Africa west of the Great Rift Valley. This monoecious plant is grown for food and as a source of oil. Its common names include egusi in Yoruba and agushi in Hausa. In English it is

known as Mann's cucumeropsis and white-seed melon [16]. The seeds are edible and oily and used like the seeds of *Citrullus lanatus*.

C. moschata, which encompasses various cultivars of pumpkin and winter squash, is cultivated in warm areas around the world as food and animal fodder. The flowers, young stems and young and ripe fruits are eaten as a vegetable. The latter are also commonly used to prepare sweets and as fodder. The seeds are eaten whole, roasted or toasted and are ground into different stews [17].

Leaves are the most widely used among the entire plant vegetative organ in taxonomy. Variations in the leaf epidermal characters have been shown experimentally to be dependent on gene as they are only slightly influenced by environmental conditions [18-19]. The basis for their use in identification and classification of many plant groups is as a result of their proven genetic stability and great structural diversity [20].

The mature leaf epidermal features, such as the pattern of epidermal cells, type of stomata, shape of guard cell pairs and ornamentation of cuticles, are considered useful in the phylogenetic studies at the level of genera or subgenera in angiosperms [21-22]. The aim of this work is to taxonomically characterize the different species of Cucurbitaceae using their epidermal features and is a part of an ongoing work on all the melons in this plant family.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sources of Materials

Fruits and seeds of the different species and varieties were collected from different parts of Rivers and Enugu states (Table 1) and sown in plastic bags containing the mixture (loamy and cow dung in the ratio 1:1).

Table 1. Sources of cucurbit materials studied.

Taxa	Serial number of species studied	Collector and accession/herbarium number	Collection date	Locality
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	001	Ajuru 023 UPH	20/02/2010	Rumuokoro, Port Harcourt
<i>C. colocynthis</i>	002	Ajuru 025 UPH	24/02/2010	Rumuokoro, Port Harcourt
<i>Cucurbita moschata</i>	003	Ajuru 030 UPH	01/04/2010	Port Harcourt fruit garden, Kaduna Street, Port Harcourt.
<i>Cucumeropsis mannii</i>	004	Ajuru 031 UPH	03/04/2010	Ozuaha farmland, Ikwerre L.G.A., Port Harcourt.
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	005	Ajuru 035 UPH	15/09/2011	Port Harcourt fruit garden, Kaduna street, Port Harcourt
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	006	Ajuru 037 UPH	17/09/2011	Port Harcourt fruit garden, Kaduna street, Port Harcourt.

For epidermal studies, matured leaves of the different species were collected. Other materials for epidermal studies included sodium hypochloride (bleach), safranin (1%), glycerine, razor blades, cork material, slides, coverslips and microscope.

2.2 Epidermal Methodology

Fresh matured leaves for the study were obtained and soaked in Petri dishes containing distilled water to rehydrate the cells after handling. The distilled water was poured out and 5 drops of 5% sodium hypochloride was placed on the leaves. The materials were carefully picked from the Petri dishes using fine forceps and placed in a watchglass containing distilled water. This was carefully rinsed in 3 changes of the distilled water and the cells adhering to the epidermis were dusted off using camel hair brush. The strip of epidermis required for observations were stained in 1% safranin for about 5 minutes, and mounted in glycerine. Photomicrographs of good preparations were taken.

The stomatal index was calculated by noting the number of stomata and the number of epidermal cells using the eyepiece graticule. The number

of stomata was divided by the number of stomata plus the number of epidermal cells multiplied by 100, thus:

$$\frac{\text{No. of stomata}}{\text{No. of stomata} + \text{No. of epidermal cells}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

The length and width of the stomata was measured using the eye-piece graticule.

3. RESULTS

The epidermal features of the taxa studied are shown in Tables 2-4.

The epidermis of the leaves of the species showed two types of cell shape; Trapezoid and irregular. Trapezoid cell shapes were found in *C. lanatus* – var. A and C, *C. sativus* and *C. manni* while *C. moschata*, *C. colocynthis*, *C. lanatus* var. B and *C. melo* had irregular cell shapes (Table 2).

The anticlinal cell wall pattern in the species was straight to sinuous in *C. moschata*, all varieties of *C. lanatus*; *C. manni*, *C. melo*, *C. sativus* and *C. manni* had straight wall patterns and *C. colocynthis* showed sinuous wall patterns (Table 2).

Table 2. Qualitative and quantitative epidermal cell characteristics of the cucurbit species studied.

Taxa	Epidermal cell shape	Anticlinal cell wall pattern	Epidermal cell length (µm)	Epidermal cell width range (µm)	Number of epidermal cells per view	Epidermal cell wall thickness (µm)
<i>C. colocynthis</i>	Irregular	Sinuous	36.29 ± 6.46	17.65 ± 4.15	202	5.10 ± 0.01
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. A	Trapezoid	Straight	34.10 ± 3.53	16.23 ± 1.75	290	2.02 ± 0.45
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. B	Irregular	Straight	34.47 ± 5.35	16.75 ± 2.15	275	2.75 ± 5.35
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. C	Trapezoid	Straight	33.58 ± 7.97	16.90 ± 3.75	360	4.97 ± 2.12
<i>C. manni</i>	Trapezoid	Straight	33.95 ± 7.25	15.53 ± 2.02	287	4.87 ± 3.15
<i>C. moschata</i>	Irregular	Straight	32.39 ± 0.26	14.95 ± 3.35	293	2.93 ± 7.75
<i>C. melo</i>	Irregular	Straight	30.57 ± 9.80	14.87 ± 2.02	304	1.37 ± 1.35
<i>C. sativus</i>	Trapezoid	Straight	32.47 ± 5.75	14.98 ± 2.05	309	1.57 ± 1.45

Results are in mean ± SD

The cell size varied from 30.57±9.80 x 14.87±2.02 µm in *C. melo*, 32.39±0.26 x 14.95±3.35µm in *C. moschata*, 33.58±7.97 x 16.90±3.75µm in *C. lanatus* var. C, 33.95±7.25 x 15.53±2.05µm in *C. manni*, 34.10±3.53 x 16.23±1.75µm in *C. lanatus* var. A, 34.47±5.35 x 16.75±2.15µm in *C. lanatus* var B to 36.29±6.46 x 17.65±4.15µm in *C. colocynthis*. The variation in the epidermal cells length and width was not much.

The cell wall thickness ranged generally from 1.37µm to 5.10µm. *C. colocynthis*, *C. lanatus* var. C and *C. manni* have closely related cell wall thickness. *C. melo* had the lowest epidermal cell wall thickness.

The average epidermal cell number per field view varied from 202 in *C. colocynthis* to 360 in *C. lanatus* var. C. It was 290 in *C. lanatus* var. A, 275 in *C. lanatus* var. B, 293 in *C. moschata*, 287 in *C. manni*, 309 in *C. sativus* and 304 in *C. melo* (Table 2).

Stomata is present on both surfaces, more abundant on abaxial than adaxial surfaces and confined to areas between veins in all the species (Table 3, Plates 1–4). Stomatal complex mostly anomocytic with 5–8 unspecialised cells around guard cells. *C. colocynthis* had the highest stomatal index of 9.01%.

Table 3. Qualitative and quantitative stomatal and trichome features of the cucurbit species studied.

Taxa	Stomatal type(s)	S.I	Trichome type	Number of trichome per cell
<i>C. colocynthis</i>	Anomocytic	9.01	Glandular multicellular	7-10
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. A	Anomocytic	5.84	Glandular multicellular & peltate	3-5
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. B	Anomocytic	6.14	Glandular multicellular	4-6
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. C	Anomocytic	5.30	Glandular multicellular	4-6
<i>C. mannii</i>	Anomocytic	5.90	Peltate	6-8
<i>C. melo</i>	Anomocytic	6.98	Glandular multicellular & Peltate	3-7
<i>C. sativus</i>	Anomocytic	7.29	Glandular multicellular	4 -5
<i>C. moschata</i>	Anomocytic	7.98	Peltate	3-6

Three types of trichomes: glandular multicellular, covering multicellular and peltate multicellular trichomes were observed on both surfaces of all the species. In *C. colocynthis*, covering multicellular and glandular multicellular trichomes were observed; all the varieties of *C. lanatus* had glandular multicellular trichomes, *C.*

moschata had covering multicellular trichomes, *C. sativus* had glandular multicellular trichomes, *C. melo* had glandular peltate trichomes, and *C. mannii* had glandular multicellular trichomes. The density and description of trichomes in the species are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of morphology and density of trichomes in the cucurbit species studied.

Taxa	Density in %	Description
<i>C. colocynthis</i>	25 – 45	More pubescent
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. A	10 – 23	Pubescent
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. B	10 – 23	Sparingly pubescent
<i>C. lanatus</i> var. C	10 – 25	Sparingly pubescent
<i>C. mannii</i>	10 – 24	Sparingly pubescent
<i>C. melo</i>	25 – 44	Pubescent
<i>C. sativus</i>	28 – 48	Pubescent
<i>C. moschata</i>	25 – 30	Pubescent

4. DISCUSSION

Epidermal cell shape in the species was generally irregular or trapezoid with straight or sinuous anticlinal wall pattern (Table 3). Epidermal evidences observed in the species studied seem to be enough diagnostic values for delimiting species and genera studied.

Vegetative and reproductive plant features are usually affected by the environment where taxa occur but the character variation in the epidermal studies carried out indicated that the taxonomic application of the diversity of epidermal morphology in Cucurbitaceae is in order. Epidermal features of these species was carried out based on the earlier report that these characters represented genetic variations and have been used to solve taxonomic problems in

certain other plant groups by taxonomists [18, 20, 23-25].

All the species of Cucurbit studied contained more stomatal density in the abaxial surfaces than in the adaxial surfaces and this corresponds to earlier work by [26-28]. It was previously reported that stomata index varied on different part of the leaves or on different leaves of same plants [29].

The stomatal type observed on the leaf epidermal layer of all the species were indications of familial affinity. Strong taxonomic relationship exists in stomatal types among these species and other members of the Cucurbitaceae, where similar characters have been used in taxa delimitation. Gill (1982) reported anomocytic and paracytic stomata as

the main stomatal character of the family Cucurbitaceae [30]. Anomocytic stomata were found in all the species studied. This difference was in place, because this could be more of an adaptation to function and environment.

Taxonomic variations on stomatal size and index useful in distinguishing species were observed on the leaf epidermal layers of the species. It has been reported the diagnostic significance of the variations in stomatal size and index in delimiting species within a genus [31-32]. While egusi melon had the highest stomatal index of 9.01, watermelons varied from 5.30 to 6.14 and other species range from 5.90-6.98.

Glandular multicellular trichomes were present on the leaf surfaces of all the species, which depicts taxonomic and evolutionary relationship. Also, some species possessed peltate trichomes. Such species include *C. lanatus* var. A, *C. melo*, *C. moschata* and *C. mannii*, and this also depicts taxonomic and evolutionary relationship. However, the ontogeny of the glandular multicellular heads differs in *C. colocynthis* where more than five glandular trichomes originated anticlinally from one cell stock. In the other four species, each glandular head originates from one cell each. Recently, it was demonstrated that the importance of stomatal ontogeny in the taxonomic delimitation of species of *Acacia* [33].

The observable epidermal characters in all the species of Cucurbit studied in this work could be used with other characters such as morphology, palynology, etc to delimit these plant species in the family

5. CONCLUSION

Results from this research showed that these species of melons studied vary in their epidermal features such that their classification into the same plant family is authenticated because they possess much similarities in their features and their grouping as different species is also in line because they possess differences to authenticate this classification.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MGA designed the study, carried out the statistical analysis and wrote the first draft of the manuscript; FWN and CWW managed the analysis and literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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